

Online Data Supplement

Supplementary Figure 1. (A) The morphology of small airway epithelial cells before and after smoke was monitored using light microscopy. (B) DIO labeled (green) exosomes were incubated with normal and AATD macrophages for 1 hour. The immunofluorescence pictures of trypsin treated cells shows green labeled exosomes inside the normal and AATD macrophages.

Supplementary Figure 2. The representative blot of protein levels of P50 in AATD macrophages with/without NF- κ B inhibitor (TPCA) accompanied with normalized bar intensities to actin (n=3).